

Performance evaluation of machine learning-based intrusion detection using UNSW-NB15 and CICICS2017 datasets

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Abstract— These days, smart devices are utilized in nearly every field, and the services provided by non-public and public companies through web servers and cloud technologies are typically managed remotely. Lamentably, because of the growing demand on the network, both malware and users are increasingly exposed to these domains. Some organizations face thousands of cyber-attacks every day. As the number of network attacks increases, it becomes difficult for traditional intrusion detection systems (IDS) to prevent these attacks. Consequently, it is important to study and evaluate intrusion detection and prevention methods. With IDS, we are able to find legitimate and illegitimate behaviour from users. Therefore, machine learning (ML) should be used to design an effective IDS for secure communication. Intrusion detection and classification can be done with ML. Classification in ML is a technique for identifying groups of samples based on training samples. Its task is to estimate a function map from the input to the output variable. Pattern classification provides this prediction by using learning techniques to find legitimate patterns in data automatically. In this paper, we analyse the effectiveness of ML-based IDS methods. Performance evaluations of these techniques are done using the UNSW-NB15, and CICICS2017 datasets. Here, we analysed ML techniques including Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees, Naive Bayes, Random Forests, K Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Logistic Regression, Quadratic Discriminant Analysis, AdaBoost Classifier, CatBoost Classifier, Gradient Boosting Classifier, LGBM Classifier, Linear Discriminant Analysis, and XGB Classifier. Moreover, to evaluate the effectiveness of these techniques, we used performance indicators like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Keywords— Machine Learning, UNSW-NB15, CICICS2017, prediction, intrusion detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the rapid development of big data, cloud technology, and smart gadgets has made us increasingly dependent on the network. Additionally, the use of the Internet has become very important in the armed forces and the business world. Therefore, information confidentiality, integrity, and security are important responsibilities. Even cyber authorities are trying to meet security needs; malware and intruders are trying to access systems, corrupt data, and change data. This situation has developed so rapidly that IDS and intrusion have now reached the level of cyber warfare. Therefore, the development of network systems should be focused on confidentiality, integrity, availability, and data security. IDS is one of the largest issues affecting network security from malicious users [1].

When dealing with big data, the use of conventional methods for detection and protection is not enough to control these attacks. ML methods are useful for detecting attacks. Numerous ML-based solutions have been proposed to detect attacks in the cloud. The biggest challenge for ML solutions is to detect these attacks with high accuracy. Any type of illegitimate behaviour on the network or gadget can be considered an intrusion. An intrusion is defined as "any activity that attempts to compromise the integrity, confidentiality, or availability of a system". IDS are tools that help to distinguish, measure, and characterize intrusion behaviour. IDS is a protection system that can detect abnormal activities [2], [3].

From a security perspective, IDS is seen as a firewall. IDS can be used in conjunction with other security mechanisms like access control, authentication systems, and encryption technologies to make the system more secure from threats. IDS can distinguish between benign and malicious behaviour using malicious traffic or threat patterns [4]. According to Dewa and Maglaras [5], data mining can help exploit and use IDS with higher accuracy and better behaviour compared to conventional IDS, which may not be

suitable for modern sophisticated attacks [6]. A need for IDS is "a low false positive rate and a high true positive rate". Network intruders can be divided into two groups: (1) External intruders: unknown individuals who use various attack methods to enter the network. (2) Internal intruder: an infected node that was once a network partner. IDS can detect both external and internal intruders, but external intruders are easier to detect. This is because the inside attacker has the necessary resources to overcome the defences put in place by authenticating the system. It could be anything like malicious attempts, leaks, penetration, or DoS. IDS can provide partial detection of these threats. A perfect IDS can detect all intrusions [7]–[9]. Depending on the deployment method, IDS can be divided into two types: (1) host intrusion detection system (HIDS): HIDS is deployed on hosts and is used to detect actions such as system file changes, multiple illegal access attempts to the host, illegal memory allocation, and abnormal CPU or I/O performance. HIDS accomplishes this by monitoring real-time traffic on the host or by examining the host's log files. (2) Network intrusion detection system (NIDS): NIDS can periodically or actively listen to network traffic to examine all packets, packet payloads, IP addresses, or ports. According to the detection method, IDS can be divided into: (1) misuse-based detection: In this case, the standard must be defined and assigned to the system. Compare the node's behaviour with its effective attack pattern. The disadvantage is that this method requires knowledge of creating attack patterns to detect new attacks and also requires new information. (2) anomaly-based detection: The basic approach is to give "normal behaviour" using automatic training. This method does not look at actual attack patterns but examines anomalous behaviour. The disadvantage of this approach is that the system may interpret invalid behaviour as valid behaviour. (3) Specification-based detection: This focuses on detecting characteristic differences that are not identified by ML or data. Standard behaviour definitions are always defined manually, and violations of these specifications are tracked. The disadvantage of this approach is that manually developing each specification is a time-consuming process for humans and lacks the ability to detect malicious behaviour that does not comply with the IDS specifications. [1]

The main purpose of this article is to provide a comparative study and performance evaluation of different ML-based IDS. The ML methods we analysed include SVM, Decision Trees (DT), Naive Bayes, Random Forests, KNN, Logistic Regression, Quadratic Discriminant Analysis, AdaBoost Classifier, CatBoost Classifier, Gradient Boosting Classifier, LGBM Classifier, Linear Discriminant Analysis, and XGB Classifier. For analysis purposes, UNSW-NB15 [11], [12] and CICIDS2017 [13] were used as the data sets, and Python was used as the programming language.

This article is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the work related to the IDS. Section 3 discusses the ML approaches, and Section 4 discusses the data sets, implementation, and experimental results. The concluding remarks of the study are presented in Section 5.

II. RELATED WORK

Myint H.O. and Meesad P. give an SVM-based incremental learning algorithm [14]. The authors used SVM for prediction. This has reduced the complexity and time required for repeated training. The authors used the KDD Cup99 dataset to measure the performance of the system. The proposed system can predict 41 types of incoming data.

Sandhya Peddabachigari et al. give an IDS based on a decision tree [15]. The authors used the 1998 DARPA dataset to measure the performance of the system. The proposed system provides better performance compared to traditional techniques. Moreover, the results show that the proposed techniques have reduced training and testing time complexity as compared to the SVM.

Mrutyunjaya Panda and Manas Ranjan Patra used Naïve Bayes for NIDS [16]. The authors used the KDD Cup99 dataset to measure the performance of the system. The obtained results show that the framework has high performance in terms of false positive rate, processing time, and cost.

Majjed et al. give a deep learning framework called STL-IDS [18]. The authors claim the proposed framework can be used for learning and dimensionality reduction. In this approach, both training and testing time are reduced to achieve higher prediction accuracy for SVM. The proposed approach provides an improvement in NIDS.

Moustafa et al. [20] give a Collaborative Anomaly Detection Framework (CADF) for processing big data in the cloud. The authors provided details for deploying this framework in the cloud. The proposed technique consists of three modules: network data capture and logging, pre-processing of this data, a

Gaussian mixture-based decision engine, and a lower-upper interquartile distance limit to detect attacks. The authors used the UNSW-NB15 dataset to measure the performance of the decision engine in a real cloud environment and compared it with three ADS strategies. Using this technique, SaaS is designed for easy deployment in a cloud environment.

Diro et al. [22] give a decentralized IDS based on deep learning for IoT. The authors recommend deploying this system on a fog computing layer. The authors used the NSL-KDD, ISCX, and KDD-CUP-99 datasets to measure the performance of the system, and the results showed 97% accuracy.

Muna et al. [23] give an ADS for industrial IoT. The authors used an unsupervised deep auto-encoder for classification and the NSL-KDD and UNSW-NB15 datasets to measure the performance of the system. The authors claim experimental results show 99% accuracy.

Garg et al. [24] give a hybrid data processing method for network malfunction detection that affects the accuracy of GWO and CNN. The accuracy of GWO and CNN training has been improved by observing initial capabilities and retrieval failures. These extensions are called improved GWO and improved CNN. The proposed model works in two phases. In the first phase, the improved GWO used feature selection to reduce the failure rate and reduce the feature set. In the second phase, the CNN is used for the separation of threats. The authors used the DARPA'98 and KDD'99 datasets to measure the performance of the system. They claim the presented cloud-based threat detection model outperforms other techniques and, compared with GWO and CNN, improves the detection rate, false alarm rate, and accuracy by 8.25%, 4.08%, and 3.62%, respectively.

Manimurugan et al. [26] give a deep belief-based IDS. The authors used the CICIDS 2017 dataset to measure the performance of the system. The given approach shows an accuracy of 97.71% for the PortScan threat and 96.37% for the infiltration threat.

Basati et al. [27] give a CNN-based IDS called deep feature extraction. The authors used UNSW-NB15, CICIDS2017, and KDD-Cup99 datasets to measure the performance of the system.

The suggested approach has been tested for both binary and multi class classifications. The authors focus on devices with lower computing power.

Rashid et al. [28] give a tree-based stacking ensemble IDS for IoT. The authors used the NSL-KDD and UNSW-NB15 datasets to measure the performance of the system. The authors improved efficiency through dimensionality reduction.

Fatani et al. [29] give dimensionality reduction by swarm intelligence (SI) for IDS. The authors used CIC2017, NSL-KDD, BoT-IoT, and KDD99 datasets to measure the performance of the system.

Keserwani et al. [30] give a combined gray wolf optimization and PSO technique to extract significant features for IoT IDS. The authors used the KDDCup99, NSL-KDD, and CICIDS-2017 datasets to measure the performance of the system.

Kasongo and Sun give an XGBoost-based feature selection technique, IDS [31]. The authors used the UNSW-NB15 dataset to measure the performance of the system. Several ML techniques were used to test the effectiveness of IDS. The author's claims that XGBoost feature selection specifically enables the decision tree to achieve the best classification performance of up to 90%.

Jing and Chen give SVM-based IDS [32]. Unlike min-max scaling, a new data scaling based on a logarithmic function was used. The authors used the UNSW-NB15 dataset to measure the performance of the system and claimed an accuracy of 85.99%.

Khan et al. give a new two-stage anomaly detection technique [33]. First, an automatic encoder is used to perform binary data classification, and then the result of binary classification is added as an extra feature to multi-classification. The authors used the KDD99 and UNSW-NB15 datasets to measure the performance of the system and claimed 99.99% and 89.13% multi class accuracy, respectively.

Rosay et al. give MLP with two layers, each containing 256 neurons, as an IDS [34]. The authors remove constant-valued features from the data. The authors used the CICIDS-2017 and CICIDS-2018 datasets to measure the performance of the system and claimed 99.46% and 95.47% accuracy, respectively.

Ho et al. give a resampling technique for IDS using the CICIDS-2017 dataset [35]. In the experiment, random under sampling, SMOTE, and their combination with the C4.5 classifier were used separately.

Ustebay et al. [36] used recursive feature elimination (RFE) as an IDS. Researchers used the top 10 features to train a deep multilayer perceptron (DMLP) classifier. The authors used the CICIDS-2017 dataset to measure the performance of the system and claimed 91% accuracy.

Kong et al. [37] give a hybrid deep learning approach combining 1D CNN and LSTM as an IDS. In the given method, the first one-dimensional CNN was used to extract spatial features. Then, the concatenated LSTM can extract temporal features, so the model can extract both temporal and spatial features simultaneously. The authors used the CICIDS-2017 dataset to measure the performance of the system and claimed 97% accuracy.

III. MACHINE LEARNING APPROACHES

A. Naïve Bayes

This algorithm is based on the Bayes theorem and is used for classification. This algorithm works by assuming that all inputs are independent.

Working:

Step 1: Given training S , calculate the probability $p(v_j)$ of each category.

Step 2: Given the training set S , calculate the conditional probability $p(a_i|v_j)$ for each feature value a_i and each feature a .

Step 3: Given an unknown instance of X' , classify X' by best likelihood.

B. Decision Tree

In a decision tree, discrete objective functions are represented by a decision tree. A decision tree classifies samples by ordering them in a tree from the root to some leaf node that provides the sample classification. Each node of the tree specifies a test for some property of the sample, and each branch descending from the node corresponds to one of the values for that property. Events are classified by starting at the root of the tree, testing the feature specified by the node, and then going to the branches corresponding to the feature in the sample. This process is then repeated for the subtree rooted at the new node.

Working:

Step 1: To place the best attribute from the dataset at the root of the tree, a mathematical measure like information gain is used.

Step 2: Divide the dataset into subsets. When partitioning, we should consider whether each subset should contain data with the same attribute value.

Step 3: Repeat steps 1 and 2 on each subset until we find leaf nodes in all branches of the tree.

C. Random Forests

It is an ensemble learning technique for classification or regression. It works by creating multiple decision trees by selecting a "K" number of data points from a dataset and then combining them to get a more accurate and stable prediction. Take the average of all "K"-point Decision Tree predictions.

Working:

Step 1: Randomly select elements 'i' from the entire element's 'j' with one condition $i \ll j$.

Step 2: Using the concept of best splitting point, calculate node 'n' from elements 'i'.

Step 3: Again, using the concept of best split, we need to split node 'n' into a child node.

Step 4: Repeat steps 1–3 until you reach node number '1'.

Step 5: Create a forest by repeating steps 1–4 for 'k' times to create a 'k' number of trees.

Step 6: To predict the target, run the test functions, use the rules of each randomly generated decision tree, and save the predicted target.

Step 7: Then simply find out the votes for each projected target.

Step 8: Finally, consider the target of the high-vote prediction as the final prediction.

D. K-Nearest Neighbour

It classifies samples based on their similarity. Euclidean distance is used to measure the similarity between samples. For each test data point, it looks at the K-nearest training data points, takes the most frequently occurring classes, and assigns that class to the test data. Therefore, K represents the number of samples close to the test sample that we will use to find the category.

Working:

Step 1: Determine the K value.

Step 2: Calculate the distance between the query samples and the entire training sample.

Step 3: Sort the distance in ascending order.

Step 4: Assign the predicted value to the query instance based on the majority of classes of nearest neighbours.

E. Support Vector Machine

In SVM, hyperplanes are used to separate instances. The distance from the boundary to the nearest instance is called the edge, and the instance closest to the distribution boundary is called the support vector. When dealing with SVMs, we need to consider two things: 1) margins should be as wide as possible, and 2) support vectors are the most important elements because they are often classified incorrectly.

Working:

Step 1: Define the best hyperplane: maximize the edge.

Step 2: Extend the definition given in step 1 for nonlinear separable problems: have a penalty term for misclassifications.

Step 3: Map the data into a high-dimensional space where it is easier to classify using linear decision surfaces: reformulate the problem so that the data is implicitly mapped into this space.

F. Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)

LDA is used for both classification and dimensionality reduction. The main goal of LDA is to find lines (or planes) that best separate samples from different groups. The main idea is that the decision boundary should be chosen to minimize the variance in class distribution while maximizing the distance between two classes. This method is called the Fisher criterion. LDA works by projecting the samples into a low-dimensional space while keeping as much information as possible and then finding the hyperplane that separates the classes according to the Fisher criterion. LDA assumes that the sample follows a Gaussian distribution and that the covariance matrices of the groups are equal.

Working:

Step 1: Calculate the mean and standard deviation of each attribute.

Step 2: Calculate within-class and between-class scatter matrices.

Step 3: Use these matrices to calculate eigenvectors and eigenvalues.

Step 4: LDA selects the k eigenvectors with the largest eigenvalues from a transformation matrix.

Step 5: LDA uses this transformation matrix to transform the data into a new k-dimensional space.

Step 6: When the transformation matrix transforms the data into a new k-dimensional space, LDA can be used for classification or dimensionality reduction.

G. Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA)

This technique is similar to LDA and assumes that the samples in each category follow a normal distribution, but does not assume that each class shares the same covariance matrix. In contrast, QDA assumes that each category has its own covariance matrix. QDA allows classifiers to evaluate non-linear relationships.

H. Logistic Regression

It uses a logistic function to map the output variables. It's called regression because it uses the output of a linear regression as input and uses a sigmoid function to predict the probability of a particular category. A sigmoid function is used to map values onto probability. Depending on the event, the result will be 0 or 1. For binary prediction, the population can be divided into two groups with a threshold of 0.5. Any value above 0.5 is considered category A, and anything below 0.5 is considered category B.

I. Boosting classifiers

Boosting is an ensemble model that tries to create a good classification with many weak classifiers. It is made by creating models by using weak models in series. First, create a model based on the training samples. A second model is then created that attempts to correct errors present in the first model. Continue this process until the training samples are estimated or the maximum number of models is added.

Working:

1. Assign equal weight to each sample in the dataset.

2. Use this input in the model and identify misclassified samples.

3. Increase the weight of misclassified samples.

4. If (what is desired is achieved)

Go to step 5.

Else

Go to step 2.

5. End

Types:

1. Gradient Boosting: It creates the final model from the sum of several weak models trained on the same data. It works on the idea of incremental addition. The first weak learner will not be trained on the dataset; instead, it simply returns the average of the column in question. The residual of the first weak learner is calculated and used as the response for the next weak learner to be trained. The second weak learner will follow the same strategy; the residue will be calculated and used as the response of the third weak learner; and so on until the residue completes zero. The dataset must be either in numeric or categorical form, and the loss function must be different to generate the residuals.

2. XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting): This is an extreme variant of gradient boosting. The main difference between XGBoost and gradient boosting is that XGBoost uses a regularization method. Additionally, it works better when the dataset contains both numeric and categorical features.

3. Adaboost: This technique also works on the principle of incremental addition, where multiple weak learners are used to get strong learners. In this case, the value of the alpha parameter will be inversely proportional to the error of weak learners.

4. CatBoost: The growth of decision trees inside CatBoost improves its performance. Decision trees created in CatBoost are symmetric. Because there is a special way of processing categorical datasets. The categorical properties in CatBoost are encoded based on the response. Consequently, when training or encoding categorical attributes, the weight of the response will be taken into account, thus increasing their accuracy on categorical datasets.

5. LGBM (Light GBM): It uses a tree-based learning algorithm and is considered a very computationally powerful algorithm. This technique grows trees vertically, i.e., from leaf to leaf. It selects the leaf with the largest loss for growth. When growing the same leaf, it can reduce the loss more than the level-wise algorithm. [27]

IV. EXPERIMENTATION

We used UNSW-NB-15 and CICIDS2017 datasets to test the performance of ML-based IDS. The experiment is performed in Google Colaboratory under python using TPU.

A. Description of the datasets

A.A.1 UNSW-NB-15

The UNSW-NB-15 dataset was created using the IXIA PerfectStorm tool at the UNSW Canberra Cyber Range Laboratory to produce a hybrid of real-world modern normal and abnormal activities to track attacks. The tcpdump tool was used to capture 100 GB of raw cloud traffic. This data includes nine types of attacks, including fuzzers, analysis, backdoors, DoS, exploits, generic, reconnaissance, shellcode, and worms. Argus, Bro-threat detection model, and a cloud monitoring tool were used, and twelve algorithms were developed to generate 49 feature and category labels.

The total number of records is 2 million and 5,40,044 are stored in the CSS file. The ground truth table is called UNSW-NB15_GT.csv, and the list of events file is called UNSW-NB15_LIST_EVENTS.csv. A subset of these datasets was created as a training set and a testing set, respectively, UNSW_NB15_training-set.csv and UNSW_NB15_testing-set.csv. The number of records in the training set is 1,75,341 records, and the test set consists of 82,332 records of different types, attacks, and normal [11], [12]

A.A.2 CICIDS2017 Dataset

CICIDS2017 dataset spanned over eight different files containing five days normal and attacks traffic data of Canadian Institute of Cybersecurity. These files are of type csv. The dataset contains attack information as five days traffic data. Dataset contains 3119345 instances and 83 features containing 15 class labels (BENIGN, DoS Hulk, PortScan, DDoS, DoS GoldenEye, FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator, DoS

slowloris, DoS Slowhttptest, Bot, Web Attack – Brute Force, Web Attack – XSS, Infiltration, Web Attack – Sql Injection, Heartbleed). [13]

B. IDS methodology used in experimentation

Fig. 1 shows the IDS methodology used in the experimentation. Specifically, the method consists of three phases: (1) dataset and pre-processing, (2) training, and (3) testing.

Fig. 1 Flowchart of the IDS methodology used in experimentation

C. Performance Metrics

Accuracy: A measure used to represent the proportion of correct classifications among the total records in the test set.

$$\text{Accuracy} = (TP + TN) / (TP + FN + TN + FP)$$

Precision (P): A measure of actual performance in the desired response area, that is, between positions.

$$P = TP / (TP + FP)$$

Recall (R): A measure of how many predicted answers are discarded, or for each correct mark, how many other correct marks we discard.

$$R = TP / (TP + FN)$$

F1 Score (F): harmonic average of two matrices P and R.

$$F = (2 * P * R) / (P + R)$$

Where,

True positive (TP): cases of anomalies are classified as true anomalies.

False positives (FP): classify normal classes as anomalies.

True negative (TN): cases that belong to the normal category and classified as normal class.

False negative (FN): cases that belong to the abnormal category and classified as normal class [7].

D. Results and Discussion

Popular ML techniques, KNN, SVM, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Quadratic Discriminant Analysis, AdaBoost Classifier, CatBoost Classifier, Gradient Boosting Classifier, LGBM Classifier, Linear Discriminant Analysis and XGB Classifier are compared. Precision, recall, precision, and F1 score are considered for comparison purposes.

D.A.1 UNSW-NB15 dataset results

The comparison results for the UNSW-NB15 data set are shown in Table 1 for different attack categories.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF MACHINE LEARNING BASED IDS FOR UNSW-NB15 DATASET RESULTS

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision		Recall		F1 Score	
		Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal
KNN	88.23	0.84	0.96	0.98	0.74	0.91	0.84
SVM	89.87	0.87	0.97	0.98	0.77	0.92	0.86
Decision Tree	85.03	0.81	0.94	0.97	0.70	0.88	0.80
Random forest	89.55	0.86	0.97	0.99	0.76	0.92	0.86
Naive Bayes	47.89	0.23	1.00	1.00	0.38	0.38	0.55
Logistic Regression	88.69	0.85	0.98	0.99	0.75	0.91	0.85
QDA	47.89	0.23	1.00	1.00	0.38	0.38	0.55
AdaBoost	88.38	0.84	0.97	0.98	0.74	0.91	0.84
CatBoost	88.95	0.85	0.97	0.98	0.75	0.91	0.85
Gradient Boosting	85.66	0.80	0.98	0.99	0.70	0.88	0.81
LGBM	89.25	0.85	0.98	0.99	0.76	0.92	0.85
LDA	90.23	0.88	0.96	0.98	0.78	0.92	0.86
XGB	90.70	0.89	0.94	0.97	0.81	0.93	0.87

D.A.2 CICIDS2017 dataset results

The comparison results for the CICIDS2017 dataset are shown in Table 2 for different attack categories.

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF MACHINE LEARNING BASED IDS FOR CICIDS2017 DATASET

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision		Recall		F1 Score	
		Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal
KNN	99.88	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Decision Tree	99.85	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Random forest	99.88	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Naive Bayes	44.18	0.99	0.33	0.23	0.99	0.37	0.50
Logistic Regression	94.49	0.80	0.97	0.86	0.96	0.83	0.97
QDA	71.35	1.00	0.66	0.37	1.00	0.54	0.79
AdaBoost	99.21	0.97	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.98	1.00
CatBoost	99.90	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Gradient Boosting	99.62	0.98	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.99	1.00
LGBM	99.91	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
LDA	92.38	0.58	0.99	0.95	0.92	0.72	0.96
XGB	99.921	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a comparative study and performance analysis of ML-based IDS. This paper presents the results of various ML techniques for attack detection. Through a literature survey, we understood that there is a need to develop a scalable and attack-resistant IDS using deep packet inspection for secure communication.

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